

THE IMPORTANCE OF USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract: Today, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that in traditional education, students are taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, while modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, study and analyze it independently, and even draw their own conclusions.

Key words: intellectual, professional activity, integrative approach, professional activity, scientific-methodical, distribution material.

Actuality: It is known that intellectual developments on a global scale require regular intellectualization of the content and essence of preparing future specialists for professional activity. As a result, a solid ground is being prepared for the training of innovative, advanced, competitive modern personnel.

Purpose of the study. Technologicalization of the educational process is an important view and stages of pedagogical activity.

Materials and methods of research. The design of the educational process in educational institutions is divided into two levels:

- a) At the level of teacher activity (designing separate parts of the educational process);
- b) It is carried out at the level of the educational manager's activities (integrated design of the educational process). In the design of the educational process, not only each component, but also the connections between them are modeled, and the design laws prepare the ground for the development of the theoretical foundations of the design principles and their application in the practice of pedagogical activity [1].

Preparation of students to acquire intellectual knowledge is carried out in the following algorithmic sequence: Preparation of students to acquire intellectual knowledge, taking into account the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Science and Creative Ability". The main goal of this direction will be to popularize the foundations and achievements of science and technology in the information space, as well as to determine measures for the promotion of relevant activities in the field of science and scientific activity [2,4].

Results of research. Creative activity is carried out in the following sequence:

Informational and educational resources should be relevant to the content of the programs providing students with the necessary skills and qualifications consists of assignments and tasks, which students should master determination of the volume of knowledge, presentation in a certain logical system, coherence and compliance with the principles of continuity, finally, to meet the principle of systematic, educational resources are appropriate for students' level of preparation it is considered appropriate [3,5].

Conclusions. The original content of innovative activity is the formation of a new technology in practice, and its result is the activity aimed at turning the invention into a project and the

project into a technology. In innovative activity, scientific imaginations are not born according to the logic of academic science, but arise from practical considerations that develop as a result of the support of modifications of the development process.

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